

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Numerical study of Decoding 3,6 and 9 in Universe and Human body for Energy to Mass

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Abstract

Scientist Nicola Tesla told that 3,6,9 is the key to the universe. Here from AUM or Nirguna Bramha or 0 to 1,2 and the series pattern 0,1,2,3,6,12,48,96 and so on forms 3,6,9 numerologically and mathematically. From Nirguna Bramha to matter anti matter creation; collision; expansion pattern of universe; creation of soul to foetus (energy to mass); radial pulsation of human body; breathing pattern; ratio of vayu, pitta and kapha, umbilical cord follows the series and 3,6,9 is the pattern. 9,6,3 is the code of energy and 3,6,9 is the code of mass.

Keywords: 3;6;9; Nirguna Bramha; Energy to mass

1. Introduction

Magnificence of 3,6,9 is the key to the universe. It is here studied that a series is formed and a mathematical and numerical method is performed to solve the code.

2. Methodology

This study objective is to find the unique pattern to before and after creation of universe to till today; soul to foetus (energy to mass); creation of galaxies; breathing pattern; umbilical cord; radial pulsation and miasmatic weightage of the human body. The study shows a series by mathematically and numerologically analysis.

3. Results and discussion

0 is referred to Nirguna Bramha or 'AUM' cosmic sound at singularity before the creation of universe. 1 is matter particle and antimatter particle state creation. 2 represents matter particle and antimatter particle collision. 3 represents first expansion pattern, creation of galaxies, creation of soul to foetus, radial pulsation, breathing pattern and miasmatic weightage (Vayu, Pitta, Kapha).

3.1 0

$$0+1 = 1$$

$$1+1 = 2$$

$$2+1 = 3$$

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$$3+2+1 = 6$$

$$1+2+3+6 = 12$$

$$1+2 = 3$$

$$1+2+3+6+12+24 = 48$$

$$4+8 = 12$$

$$1+2 = 3$$

$$1+2+3+6+12+24+48 = 96$$

$$9+6 = 15$$

$$1+5 = 6$$

$$1+2+3+6+12+24+48+96 = 192$$

$$1+9+2 = 12$$

$$1+2 = 3$$

$$1+2+3+6+12+24+48+96+192 = 384$$

$$3+8+4 = 15$$

$$1+5 = 6$$

$$3+6+3+6 = 18$$

$$1+8 = 9$$

$$3.2. 1+2+3+6+12+24+48+96+192+384 = 768$$

$$7+6+8 = 21$$

$$2+1 = 3$$

$$1+2+3+6+12+24+48+96+192+384+768+1536 = 2976$$

$$2+9+7+6 = 24$$

$$2+4 = 6$$

$$1+2+3+6+12+24+48+96+192+384+768+2976 = 4512$$

$$4+5+1+2 = 12$$

$$1+2 = 3$$

$$3+6+6+3 = 18$$

$$1+8 = 9$$

4. Conclusion

From before birth of universe 0 or AUM or Nirguna Bramha formation of matter and antimatter; collision between matter and antimatter even expansion pattern of universe; creation of galaxies; creation of soul to foetus(energy to mass); radial pulsation of human body; breathing pattern and miasmatic weightage of human body Vayu 3, Pitta 6, Kapha 9 this series and 3,6,9 pattern is observed. 9,6,3 represents energy and 3,6,9 represents mass pattern.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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